

Remote Sensing of Marine Litter

OPTIMAL - Optical methods for Marine Litter detection

Final Report (D7)

Issue 2.0

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CONTRACT REPORT

The work described in this report was done under ESA contract.

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1 Project Overview

Manmade discarded material is an increasing global concern because of its increased production, its worldwide distribution and its impacts on the environment and, potentially, on human health. Ultimately, most of the manmade litter ends up in the marine environment, and informed policy action is needed to minimise potential impacts. The current understanding of the marine litter problem is limited due to sparse and diverse observations, therefore an observational capability should be put in place to support a better understanding of the pathways, accumulation areas and risks of the marine litter in the marine environment.

As a first step in this direction, in 2017, the European Space Agency (ESA) solicited projects to investigate potential observation scenarios to develop measurement requirements that could be translated into engineering requirements to develop a potential Earth Observation system for measuring marine debris remotely. The solution proposed by PML in the frame of the OPTIMAL (Optical Methods for Marine Litter detection) project consisted of:

1. A definition of the user requirements, through a consultation with users.
2. A revision of the current technology available.
3. Experimental tests using spectral radiometry, through laboratory experiments, an in situ campaign and satellite data analysis.
4. A scientific development plan.

The project was delivered over 12 months, articulated around the three main activities. The initial activity was to engage with users to define scenarios and to synthesise their observational requirements. These users needs were used to define experimental tests performed during the project. During the second phase, experimental tests were carried out to evaluate the feasibility of the approaches identified by users and a review of available observation technologies. Additional tests were performed to satisfy feedback from users. During the synthesis phase, the different experimental results were used to delimit further the observational requirements initially defined. The project ended with an assessment phase, during which a development plan to further refine of observational requirements for marine litter detection was outlined.

2 Scope of the document

This report presents the Final Report for OPTIMAL (D7). It provides a succinct summary of the work carried out in this project. This report includes a brief introduction to the scientific background, development of user requirements and main results from the experimental and modelling phases, scientific impact and assessment, concluding with a forward look and final remarks.

3 Introduction : general problem and the scientific background of marine plastic debris

Most of the manmade debris arriving to the marine environment is made out of artificial polymers or plastic debris. Plastic production has grown exponentially over the last 70 years. During this

time, large quantities of plastic debris have entered the world oceans. It is estimated that between 4.8 and 12.7 million metric tonnes of plastic debris entered the ocean from terrestrial sources in 2010 alone (Jambeck et al., 2015). The input from maritime activities and the accidental or deliberate disposal of plastic at sea remains largely unquantified, although it has been estimated that such objects represent 20% of all ocean plastic (Gregory and Ryan, 1997). Despite these large inputs of plastic to the ocean, a recent survey of surface ocean data, used in conjunction with a particle-tracking model, estimated that just 269,000 metric tons float at or near the surface of the ocean (Eriksen et al., 2014). The cause for the apparent mismatch between the amount of plastics entering the oceans and that detected in open ocean surveys remains largely unknown.

Marine litter is explicitly one of the 11 descriptors of a Good Environmental Status (GES) that need to be monitored, in the context of European Union (EU) Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) [2008/56/EC]. EU states are committed to ensuring the "properties and quantities of marine litter do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment". EU member states must implement monitoring protocols to assess if GES has been achieved or maintained and also to assess the progress towards GES for the marine litter descriptor (Descriptor 10). Following this Directive, there are several areas for which Indicators of the GES need to be monitored: litter on the coastlines, in the water column and floating, on the seafloor, in the biota and microplastics. Monitoring protocols have been evaluated for these Indicators, but very few include remote sensing techniques (TSG-ML, 2013). Some of these characteristics are not accessible to remote sensing (e.g. litter in the biota). But for the rest of Indicators, the potential of observation from remote sensing is, as yet, largely unknown. Similarly to the MSFD, the United Nations have adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and is in the process of structuring the monitoring of the progress towards achieving those by the use of SDG indicators. The indicator for marine pollution (SDG 14.1.1) specifically refers to marine plastic litter, and the index is under construction, with a potential role for remote sensing (GESAMP, 2019).

The scientific community, regulators and society, in a wider sense, need a more detailed global picture of the plastic in the ocean. If a better estimate of marine plastic litter could be obtained using support from remote sensors, this would have a significant impact in addressing both fundamental scientific questions as well as providing tools for environmental monitoring for the benefit of the society.

In January 2016 a NASA sponsored Workshop on Mission Concepts for Marine Debris Sensing was held which aimed to "review existing and emerging technologies that could be capable to remotely survey the state of marine debris in the ocean and on land", (http://iprc.soest.hawaii.edu/NASA_WS_MD2016/meeting.php).

The conclusions from this Workshop highlighted that the specifications of current ocean observing missions are marginally relevant to the marine litter problem, as they were not specifically designed for marine litter detection.

It was found that no unique technology was capable to cover all aspects of plastic monitoring in the marine environment. Rather, existing observational techniques from remote sensing (high-resolution optical imaging, ocean colour, synthetic aperture radar - SAR) could be adapted for monitoring different features of marine litter.

This would imply significant adaptation/validation/calibration efforts (Maximenko et al., 2016). In addition to the existing technologies, the capabilities of potential new sensors (e.g. hyperspectral, high spatial resolution, lidar, passive and active signals) can be seen as a way to expand their utility by the user community towards the problem of monitoring release and distributions of marine litter. It is expected that the progressive and systematic integration of modified techniques with new

technology will lead to a marine litter observing system which can revolutionise current views on the marine litter problem.

The OPTIMAL project has followed this approach by testing experimentally the current observation capabilities from ocean colour sensors. This has been done for two pre-selected scenarios: micro and nano plastics in the water and large plastics on the shoreline. Following the user community feedback during an ESA sponsored workshop (Dec. 2017), the study was extended to include a third scenario: large floating debris. Figure 1 summarises the work flow carried out during OPTIMAL.

Figure 1: Diagram describing the work flow of the OPTIMAL project.

4 Observation scenarios

In a recent review, the marine plastic modelling community identified the oceanic reservoirs and fluxes where marine plastics need to be quantified (Hardesty et al., 2017). This diagram is reproduced here in Figure 2 was used initially in OPTIMAL to identify the reservoirs and processes that could be observed through Earth Observation techniques.

Hardesty et al. (2017)

Figure 2: Reservoirs and fluxes of plastic debris in the marine environment (Hardesty et al., 2017). In red areas where the contribution from Earth Observation techniques have been identified as important.

Through a literature review, an online questionnaire and a user consultation workshop co-organised with ESA in the ESTEC centre (30-Nov and 1-Dec 2017), the initial requirements for marine litter remote observations have been collected. The User Requirements (D1 and D2) have been iterated and submitted to the peer reviewed literature (Martinez-Vicente et al. 2019, See Appendix).

4.1 Literature review

4.1.1 Standing stock of microplastics

In the ocean, macroplastics (diameter >5 mm) account for a substantial mass of ocean plastics, but data available are difficult to model because of: differences in methods for quantification (from non-quantitative opportunistic sightings to rigorous sampling methods e.g. (Williams et al., 2011)); smaller abundances (in number per volume) than microplastics; accumulation and drift patterns differences (because of their larger size, buoyancy and resistance to wind). For these reasons, most models of plastic accumulation refer to microplastics (Maximenko et al. 2012; Lebreton et al. 2012; van Sebille et al., 2014). Further, the majority of these models have been developed for oceanic waters. The most recent comparison of such models (van Sebille et al., 2015), highlighted that even in the most sampled areas, with higher concentrations of microplastics (e.g. Northern Pacific and Atlantic Gyres), models disagreed significantly on microplastic abundance estimates (i.e. up to a factor 10). In areas of lower accumulation of microplastics (30-70% of the total microplastics) are areas where least sampling occurs (e.g. Equatorial regions and Southern Ocean) and disagreement between models exceeds a factor of 100 (van Sebille et al., 2015). Therefore, an improvement

in the detection of surface/subsurface microplastics in the Open Ocean would help with reducing uncertainties in predictions of models, analogous to how the improvements of detection in surface Chlorophyll-a concentration provide a validation dataset for global ocean biogeochemical models.

The models' needs therefore dictate the Mission Requirements for this scenario. Firstly, the characteristics and abundances of the plastics modelled need to be defined. The methods for in situ collection of microplastics determine the size range of the plastics: a manta net with a mesh size of 0.333 mm is most commonly used in the ocean, with plastic particles counted up to 5 mm in size. This requirement is in line with monitoring recommendations from the MSFD which proposes to have a minimum resolution of size bins of 0.1 mm, starting from 20 μ m (so 20 μ m-100 μ m, 101-200 μ m, 201-300 μ m, etc.) (TSG-ML, 2013). Typical sampling techniques regularly miss the smallest size range, which may be the largest particle pool (in terms of abundances). Maximum concentrations in subtropical gyres predicted by models are \sim 108 particles Km⁻². Those maximum particle concentrations would be comparable to surface observations in the Atlantic Gyre \sim 1 - 5 particles m⁻³ in the water column, but exponentially decaying rapidly down to 5 m depth (Reisser et al., 2015). Relative uncertainty or precision of the median predicted values is \sim 80% (van Sebille et al., 2015).

In order to be directly comparable with model results, remote sensing data would need similar spatial and temporal characteristics. State-of-the-art particle dispersion models have a global coverage (Maximenko et al. 2012; Lebreton et al. 2012; van Sebille et al., 2014), but different spatial resolutions, from 1/2° (\sim 50 Km) to 1/12° (\sim 10 Km). Because of their low density, with respect to water, they are close to the surface or on the surface of the water (Kooi et al., 2016). Temporal resolution required by current global models of microplastics is primarily limited by the in situ data availability, as some models can produce daily outputs (Lebreton et al., 2012). Composition requirements come from in situ data observations at two levels. Initially, colour of microplastics collected is noted by visual inspection with the microscope. A further level of analysis, using FT-IR or Raman spectroscopy, can indicate the chemical composition (Hidalgo-Ruz et al., 2012).

This Observational Scenario focuses on microplastics in the open ocean, however coastal zones can also be targeted for model validation purposes (Critchell and Lambrechts, 2016). In this first iteration we summarise only the requirements referred to the open ocean.

A preliminary priority order for these requirements can be set, being most important detection for the purpose of providing data for validation of models. Then concentrations would be important to reduce current uncertainties in the estimates from models. Finally, it would be desirable to obtain properties of the particles, such as particle sizes or composition. All of this at a temporal frequency that would be higher than the current in situ estimates, which are normally composites (annual climatologies).

4.1.2 Accumulation of macroplastics on the shoreline

It has been highlighted that marine litter studies in the water column are centred on micro sized plastics. In contrast, in the shoreline, most of the monitoring effort has been focused on large sized litter, mostly, but not only composed of plastics (i.e. including glass, metal and wood). Macroplastics (2.5 cm < Diameter < 1 m) sizes are commonly measured by monitoring agencies. The accumulation of debris on the shoreline is influenced by anthropogenic factors such as marine activity including shipping and fishing, as well as proximity to cities and areas of high population density (Hoellein et al., 2014). Ocean currents, wind and wave action influence the distribution of marine litter and along with coastal morphology may cause accumulation on the shoreline (Duckett

and Repaci, 2016). This accumulation on the beach can heavily impact on tourism and human health and well-being (Wyles et al., 2015).

To understand the scale of the marine anthropogenic litter problem on beaches and inform the development of effective management strategies, it is necessary to conduct monitoring programmes that follow trends in levels of pollution as well as identify pathways and sources (Critchell and Lambrechts, 2016). Such monitoring is required of EU member states by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) which aims to achieve good environmental status of EU waters by 2020. Current monitoring of marine litter on beaches is done globally and regionally following different protocols and guidelines: UNEP (Cheshire et al., 2009); OSPAR (OSPAR-Commission, 2010b); NOAA (Lipiatt et al., 2013); MSFD (TSG-ML, 2013). Although significant effort is being done to unify these protocols, there seems an urgent requirement for a unifying monitoring tool.

An advantage of the above monitoring methods is that it can provide a high level of detail of the nature of marine litter items, as these are usually recorded according to a list of over 100 categories (e.g. plastic drink bottle). This can help to establish the link to specific economic sectors or origin (e.g. fisheries, coastal tourism) and determine trends in occurrence of specific types of litter. Furthermore, beach litter surveys are relatively low cost in comparison with water column sampling or deep benthic sampling. This is due to the involvement of voluntary groups that not only collect data but also contribute to the actual beach clean. Several databases exist and are publicly accessible (TSG-ML, 2011). Further, there are now “citizen science” apps to upload data into the web, like MarineLitterWatch app (EEA, EU), Marine Debris Tracker (NOAA, USA) or Marnoba (Spain). However, as yet, there has been no effort to link those sources of information to remote sensing. To do so, the characteristics of beach monitoring must dictate the requirements for this observational scenario.

Standard protocols recommend that a beach should be monitored at least 4 times in a year. Yet it has been found that surveys at regular intervals of four weeks would make multi-year trend monitoring results more reliable than current monitoring frequencies, to avoid variations due to meteorological artefacts (Schulz et al., 2015). Quantification of marine litter should be carried out along 100 m of beach length. This sampling should be done in a representative sub-selection of beaches, representative of a certain length of coast (TSG-ML, 2013). Litter should be quantified in units per square meter and by weight. For instance, some areas of the North Sea show maxima of 7,000 items per 100 m and minima of 0 items per 100 m. In terms of size, a lowest limit of 2.5 cm is recommended, thus excluding microplastics and mesoplastics ($5 \text{ mm} < \text{Diameter} < 2.5 \text{ cm}$). Concerning composition, a list of 217 different codes of items is proposed for the MSFD. This list encompasses items of different shapes, colour and composition, therefore it is very difficult to produce a requirement on composition. If possible it would be useful to have a technique that estimates the plastic proportion within a pixel.

The priority here goes first to detection, which already would enhance current monitoring techniques. Then, percentage coverage should be reliably provided. Then long term monitoring would help eliminate weather dependent variability. Finally, it would be very difficult to obtain composition or size estimates that can match the current level of detail in the in situ observations.

4.2 Questionnaire

An online questionnaire was designed on the basis of previous requirements analysis questionnaires, notably those used for the User requirements definition in previous ESA funded projects (RBD-POCO, 2015; OC-CCI, 2015). The questionnaire was circulated among a population (N=45) of in-

ternational experts. The invitation to participate in the questionnaire was sent to experts identified by: their membership in the SCOR working group 153 Floating Litter and its Oceanic Transport Analysis and Modelling (FLOTSAM), by ESA and by PML through the literature review. Figure 3 provides information about the characteristics of the respondent population.

Figure 3: Characteristics of the population sampled using the online questionnaire (N=18). A) Percentage of the nationality of the responses. B) Percentage of responses classified as user type: marine litter expert or remote sensing specialist. C) Answers recorded for the question: *What is your main application or scientific subject(s) of interest*. Question with multiple answers allowed.

A detailed analysis of the questionnaire results is provided in Report D1-D2 of the project. However, a summary of the conclusions is given here. The first aim of the online questionnaire was to quantitatively validate the Observational Scenarios initially addressed by OPTIMAL. Admittedly, there were a small number of responses recorded, but they were representative of interests, research areas and expertise. However, the main conclusion is that the initial Observational Scenarios chosen by OPTIMAL remain valid, and should be extended by:

- Extending the investigation of microplastics in the water column to the continental shelf, since it is also deemed important and no difference in requirements were noted.

- Extending the investigation of macro plastics in the water column to the continental shelf and open ocean.
- Extending detection and quantification of sources and pathways of input of plastics in the marine environment. In particular rivers and shipping industry (accidental or mismanaged), is deemed a very important top level scientific question.

The second aim of the User Questionnaire was to validate and refine the a-priori observational requirements. For both micro and macroplastics detection, the sufficient requirements (threshold) were more stringent than those initially defined from the literature review (Section 4.1), and there is a broad agreement on this from both communities represented in the questionnaire. In terms of additional desirable information, size distribution and long term accumulation detection dominates over being able to determine composition.

4.3 Compliance Matrix

Following the literature review, user consultation questionnaire and user workshop, an initial Compliance Matrix was produced during OPTIMAL (Table 2). In addition to the users requirements, a technology review was performed and current ESA radiometric missions were matched to the users requirements (OPTIMAL Deliverable 3). According to these results , the scientific questions for remote sensing of marine litter emerging are (Martínez-Vicente et al., 2019):

- Question 1 (Q1): What are the magnitude, location and temporal variability of the sources and pathways into the marine environment of marine plastic debris?
- Question 2 (Q2): What are the abundance, horizontal distribution and composition of marine plastic debris, and how do these attributes change over time?
- Question 3 (Q3): Where does marine plastic debris tend to accumulate?
- Question 4 (Q4): How is marine plastic debris transported and what are the dominant physical processes influencing its fate?
- Question 5 (Q5): What role do biological, chemical and photochemical interactions play in controlling the movement and degradation of marine plastic debris?

Table 2: Major marine processes affecting the fate of marine plastic debris and their relevance to identified scientific questions (Section 4.2). Spatial extent and lifetime of processes are reported alongside corresponding spatial and temporal sampling requirements (Martínez-Vicente et al., 2019). Sampling requirements are reported in terms of threshold levels, see text for definition. Last column list matching potential ESA current missions and sensors.

Marine Process	Spatial		Temporal		Question (Q)	Matching mission
	Spatial Extent (max)	Required Spatial Resolution of Observations	Lifetime of Process (max)	Required Frequency of Observations		
River discharge	~100 km	~20 m	~1 month	at least every 12 h	Q1	Sentinel-2 MSI
Spills	~100 km	~20 m	~1 month	at least every 24 h	Q1	Sentinel-2 MSI
Shoreline accumulation	~1000 km	~20 m	~10 year	at least every 30 d	Q1, Q2, Q3	Sentinel-2 MSI
Submesoscale convergence filaments	~10 km	100 m	~10 d	at least every 24 h	Q2, Q3	Sentinel-3 OLCI

The conclusion of this part of the project was that experimental work should be performed to ascertain the potential of radiometric sensors on Sentinel-2 and 3 to detect plastic debris in the Observation scenarios listed in Table 2.

5 Experimental phase

During OPTIMAL, three experiments were performed to refine the requirements from the observation scenarios defined by users. The first was a laboratory experiment concerning optical properties of small size plastic particles (size < 50 μm , hereafter small plastics) and their potential detectability using radiometric sensors like OLCI on Sentinel-3. The second was a field campaign deploying plastic targets on a beach to verify detectability of spectral features on remote sensing reflectance from an aircraft and the compatibility with detection using MSI from Sentinel-2. The third experiment was an investigation using Sentinel-2 MSI imagery to test detection of accumulation of floating marine plastics. Details of the methodology and results are detailed in other documents (D4-D5 reports from OPTIMAL) and only salient aspects will be presented hereafter.

5.1 Laboratory experiments and simulations of small plastics (size < 50 μm) at the Ocean surface: testing a Sentinel-3 like approach

The laboratory experiment followed an experimental design shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Process diagram for the laboratory experiment design.

5.1.1 Methods

We investigated the potential contribution of current estimates of small sized plastic particles (size < 50 μm) concentrations to the remote-sensing reflectance just above the surface of the water ($R_{rs}(\lambda)$) in the visible part of the light spectrum (400 to 700 nm). This approach has been used in the literature to include several types of planktonic organisms, bubbles and detritus (Stramski et al., 2001), as well as minerals (Wozniak and Stramski, 2004), volcanic ash (Browning et al., 2015) and different types of phytoplankton (Shang et al., 2014; Xi et al., 2017).

The approach for this study was to model the modification of normalised remote sensing reflectance above water, $R_{rs}(\lambda)$, due to the presence of small plastics. To do so, we followed standard practice (Shang et al., 2014) and modelled $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ as a function of the total absorption coefficient, $a(\lambda)$, and the total backscattering coefficient, $b_b(\lambda)$, (see Appendix A for symbols, definitions and units), which, for optically deep waters (Gordon et al., 1988; Lee et al., 2002), can be written as:

$$R_{rs}(\lambda) = \frac{0.52 \times r_{rs}(\lambda)}{(1.0 - 1.7 \times r_{rs}(\lambda))} \quad (1)$$

where $r_{rs}(\lambda)$ is below-water remote-sensing reflectance, which is related to $a(\lambda)$ and $b_b(\lambda)$ through:

$$r_{rs}(\lambda) = \left[0.09 + 0.13 \times \frac{b_{bp}(\lambda)}{(a(\lambda) + b_b(\lambda))} \right] \times \frac{b_b(\lambda)}{(a(\lambda) + b_b(\lambda))} \quad (2)$$

The $a(\lambda)$ and $b_b(\lambda)$ are described by the linear combination of the contributions by optically active components (Kirk, 1994; Mobley, 1994). In order to simulate the small plastics effects on R_{rs} we assumed that the optically active components were: pure seawater, a generic phytoplankton (*phy*) and small plastics (μP):

$$a(\lambda) = a_w(\lambda) + a_{phy}(\lambda) + a_{\mu P}(\lambda) \quad (3)$$

$$b_b(\lambda) = b_{bw}(\lambda) + b_{bphy}(\lambda) + b_{b\mu P}(\lambda) \quad (4)$$

We assumed, initially, that no differences arose from on the optical properties of the dissolved matter. The reference simulation included pure seawater and generic phytoplankton components in 3 and 4. Pure seawater absorption ($a_w(\lambda)$) and backscattering ($b_{bw}(\lambda)$) coefficients were taken from the literature (Morel, 1974; Pope and Fry, 1997) and kept constant. The variations of the phytoplankton absorption coefficient ($a_{phy}(\lambda)$) were modelled following (Bricaud et al., 1998), as a function of chlorophyll-a concentrations (*Chl*, in mgm^{-3}). *Chl* was changed from $0.02 mgm^{-3}$ to $5.0 mgm^{-3}$, encompassing most of the variability of oceanic and coastal waters. Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the resulting simulated spectra of a_{phy} and b_{bphy} for the range of *Chl* considered.

Figure 5: Model of the absorption coefficient of phytoplankton using Bricaud et al. (1988) used in the *Chl* range between 0.05 and 5 mgm^{-3} .

Figure 6: Model of the backscattering coefficient of phytoplankton using Morel and Maritorena (2001).

Particle-specific optical properties of small plastics (or particle cross-sections) were measured through laboratory experiments, whereas realistic estimates of small plastics concentration in the marine environment were obtained from the literature. Experimental details can be found in D4-D5 reports. Figure 7 shows the laboratory experimental setup used, with its different instruments.

Figure 7: Experimental setup used to measure the optical properties of small plastics.

In order to quantify the effect of small plastics on *Chl* retrieval, we used the NASA OC4v4 standard algorithm for processing ocean colour applicable to global estimates of *Chl* from ocean colour sensors (hereafter *OC4Chl*). Because the coefficients of this empirical reflectance ratio are reviewed periodically, as new *in situ* data become available, the latest online version has been used (https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/atbd/chlor_a/ visited October 2018).

The input values to the OC4v4 algorithm were $b_b/(a + b_b)$ spectra derived from the laboratory experiments. The possible combinations of small plastics sizes and their concentrations and *Chl* were then explored in the form of a ratio between *OC4Chl* computed from the standard phytoplankton model with small plastics and the *OC4Chl* computed from the standard phytoplankton model only.

5.1.2 Results

In order to provide understanding to the potential effects of small plastics on radiometrically retrieved properties (like *Chl*), we compared the deviation on the *OC4Chl* caused by small plastics with current estimates in uncertainty of *Chl* retrieval. This is a first order approximation, but it is relevant because it takes into account the uncertainty of the whole system, including the final

biogeochemical product, rather than focussing only on the uncertainty of the different parts of the system (i.e. radiometric uncertainty from instrument, from atmospheric correction, from inversion algorithms).

Recent estimates of uncertainty in satellite retrieved *Chl* (Brewin et al., 2016), reported an average root mean square errors of 0.157 (in \log_{10} space). This corresponds to $\pm 50\%$ uncertainty in $Chl=0.05 \text{ mgm}^{-3}$ in the linear space. Some useful insights can be obtained by comparing this uncertainty value to the modelling results from this experiment. Results are being worked up in the form of a paper to be submitted in the scientific literature.

5.1.3 Conclusions and further research

The aim of this study was to validate and to refine the observational requirements for microplastic detection in the ocean. In our definition of microplastic we consider plastics less than $5000\mu\text{m}$ in size, and we have focussed the study around those sizes (2.0 and $20 \mu\text{m}$) which are expected to have greater contribution to the ocean colour radiometry at the scale of existing and planned platforms (e.g. Sentinel-3, VIIRS, MODIS and the future PACE mission).

According to the Compliance Matrix (D3), the target for this approaches is the anomalies caused in the water leaving radiances by the presence of small plastics. These radiometric anomalies translate ultimately into biogeochemical products, such as Chlorophyll concentrations. The approach in this study was to provide boundaries of detectability with expected concentrations of small plastics for a set of model plastic particles (i.e. polystyrene beads).

Using a standard chlorophyll algorithm (which only requires remote sensing reflectance values at 4 wavelengths) we analysed the potential deviations from chlorophyll retrievals when there are small plastics in the water, in idealised sampling and modelling conditions. We found that:

- An upper boundary for concentrations of small plastics of 2.0 and $20 \mu\text{m}$ diameter has been provided. Furthermore, the "optical anomaly" caused by small plastics would be more noticeable in areas of $Chl < 0.05 \text{ mgm}^{-3}$.
- Assumptions made in this study on the size distribution and the absorption characteristics of the small plastics could dampen or enhance, respectively, the predicted effects on the water colour. These effects need to be further assessed through additional experiments and modelling. Similarly, the lack of *in situ* small plastics quantification for validation at optically relevant sizes, in combination with optical data limits the validation of this experiment.
- The increase in accuracy of the remote sensing system by a factor 10 would allow detection close to the maximum predicted small plastics concentrations in low *Chl*. This result has been achieved without increasing the number of wavelengths used.

Overall, the upper boundaries of detection for small plastics concentrations provided in this study are a first approximation, obtained in simplified laboratory and modelling conditions. These boundaries may change when considering realistic optical properties and need further investigation. Despite the potential limitations of this study, it has been found that enhancement of the sensitivity of the radiometric measurements is critical to achieve detection of small plastics.

5.2 Field campaign and simulations of large plastic accumulations (size >10 m) at the shoreline: testing a Sentinel-2 like approach

A field campaign was conducted incorporating *in situ* hyperspectral radiometry measurements, airborne hyperspectral data and Sentinel-2B MSI concurrent imagery. The aim of this campaign was to evaluate the detection of large marine plastics on the shore and provide guidance for further system development to ESA. More precisely, the results of this campaign provided some guidance in what is the minimum sensor spectral resolution and optimal pixel size to detect plastics on the shore.

5.2.1 Methods

Field measurements were carried out in May and June 2018 (with in-situ data acquisition with Sentinel-2B overpass taking place on 15/05/2018 and airborne data collected on 26/06/2018) on the shore of Whitsand Bay (UK). Four different plastic targets were deployed with sizes ranging from 7 m x 7 m to approximately 9 m x 12 m (Figure 8):

- 2 plastic targets from the National Environment Research Council Field Spectroscopy Facility NERC-FSF with colours grey and black.
- 2 types of agricultural fleece plastics targets.

Measurements of the targets remote sensing reflectance were collected with an Analytical Spectral Device (ASD) FieldSpec Pro hyperspectral spectroradiometer. Aerosol content was recorded by a simultaneously operated Microtops sunphotometer during both sampling days. The GPS locations of each target were recorded thanks to the GPS system of the Microtops sunphotometer.

Figure 8: Targets deployed in Whitsand Bay on 26th June 2018. Photo taken on a Phantom 4 DJI drone, caption courtesy of the "The Plastic Tide".

A hyperspectral imager (Specim Aisa Fenix) operated by the NERC Airborne Research Facility, collected data from their aircraft at five different altitudes between 750 m and 2200 m on 26th June 2018. The Aisa Fenix has 622 spectral bands and 384 pixels in its 31.94° of FOV (Field Of View). It covers the region of spectra from 380 nm to 2500 nm with a Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) that ranges between 500-1000 and a spectral resolution of 3.5 nm in the VNIR and 12 nm for the SWIR region (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Left capture shows true color composite of unmapped atmospherically corrected Fenix data. Right capture is highlighting the Regions Of Interest created for the white target, black target and sand in the colours of red, green and blue respectively.

Finally, Sentinel-2B data were extracted from the corrected matching scene in 3 x 3 windows (Figure 10), centred on the GPS locations of the centre of the targets. Due to the size of the targets being smaller than 10 x 10 m, and MSI pixel resolutions between 10 - 60 m, only the centre pixel value was used, as averaging the window significantly reduced the signal of the target in the resulting mean pixel.

Figure 10: Figures show Sentinel-2B MSI from 15th May 2018 over the Rame Peninsula (UK). Data have been atmospherically corrected using the Sen2Cor software (Main-Knorn et al., 2017).

In addition to the *in situ*, aircraft and satellite data collection, radiative transfer modelling was done using 6S code to assess performance of different waveband widths. The *in situ* data were used in combination with the radiative transfer model 6S (Second Simulation of the Satellite Signal in the Solar Spectrum (Vermote et al., 1997)) to compute remote sensing reflectance at the satellite height. The 6S simulation was done via the Python wrapper Py6S (Wilson, 2013) on a semi-automated procedure.

5.2.2 Results

The reflectance collected *in situ* (Figure 11) confirms previous observations concerning radiance of marine plastics in the short wave infrared (Garaba et al., 2018). Similar reflectance features were obtained from the radiometer mounted on the aircraft (see D4-D5 for full details).

Figure 11: Mean in-situ reflectance for each target as recorded in the ASD instrument. The bands with higher standard deviation correspond to water vapour absorption bands (1350-1420 nm and 1800-1920 nm) and have been therefore masked out. The grey dashed vertical lines highlights the wavelengths 1215 nm and 1732 nm that most commonly show absorption features for different plastics.

Using the aircraft mounted hyperspectral radiometer data, we computed the Hydrocarbon Index, HI (Kühn et al., 2004), was originally suggested for detecting hydrocarbons and compared it with a PML constructed index based on the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index, the Normalised Difference Hydrocarbon Index (NDHI). Figure 12 highlights the advantage of using NDHI over HI in our field campaign.

Figure 12: Using the lowest altitude Aisa Fenix atmospherically corrected data, from left to right we have: ENVI true colour composite, grey scale HI index and grey scale NDHI index with values below 0 also masked to 0. Center and right image have been created using the Band Math tool in ENVI. For both center and right images, bright pixels are associated with high values of their respectively index.

5.2.3 Conclusions and further work

Detection of macro plastics on the shore by optical sensors remains a challenge. This study has focused in the 1732 nm of the absorption feature common to many types of plastics (and usually suggested in the literature for identification of hydrocarbons and plastics on the sea) which also has the potential to detect plastics on the shore. We also have highlighted how using plastic's reflectance rather than their radiance still shows clear absorption features for those types of plastics and can facilitate their identification. This effect indicates that multispectral sensors in the SWIR could be used for plastic detection as the absorption features of some plastics are not only visible in hyperspectral data.

We have used the HI index over the Fenix atmospherically corrected airborne data and we have concluded that it can be used on the shore as well but need some modifications as its use can lead to misinterpretation. This is largely caused because the sand gives highly variable HI values that can be also positive and within range of plastics. However, the absorption features are still visible in the reflectance spectra so we have proposed a new index called NDHI (as a simile to NDVI) that gives another promising starting point for plastic detection.

The use of this index thanks to the 1732 nm feature in combination with algorithms for suitable threshold and preprocessing could facilitate plastic detection. Our use of the Sentinel-2B data and the 6S simulations suggest that multispectral sensors could also be used if they meet the bands criteria highlighting the possibility of not using hyperspectral data. The NDHI performs well independently of the GSD always having in mind that in our study the ground pixel was totally covered by plastic. Further studies could refine the percentage of sand that has to be covered by

plastic to give a positive in the detection of plastics using NDHI.

In order to design a new sensor that could identify plastics thanks to the use of a band in 1732 nm, we have analysed 6S simulations to assess the optimal pixel resolution and bandwidth. We need the bandwidth at 1732 to be small enough to not get close to the water vapor region and not in contact with the response of other bands in the sensor. No clear tendency or optimum value of that bandwidth could be identified by comparing the sand and plastic modeled response but the bandwidth should allow a good ground resolution. Therefore we recommend a 40 nm bandwidth as a good compromise and for being the length of absorption feature as seen in the airborne hyperspectral data. We also analysed the effect on how different pixel sizes affect this index when the entire extension of the pixel is covered in plastic and we obtained that the sand and plastics are following the same trend. This implies that the adjacent pixels are not causing the absorption features to disappear, meaning the index could also be used for plastic detection with different pixel sizes as long as its extension is covered in plastics. If the pixel is not totally covered by plastics, its minimum coverage percentage needs to be identified in further studies. This will be an important issue for designing a satellite to detect plastic but it is not a big restriction for airborne data with better ground pixel resolution such as sensors mounted in aircrafts or even drones that can usually achieve centimetres of ground resolution.

5.3 Satellite image analysis for detection of floating debris aggregations (size > 10 m): testing a Sentinel-2 like approach

To date, only a few studies have explored the potential applications of satellite remote sensing for detecting macroplastics on surface ocean waters (Garaba et al., 2018). As spatial resolution, temporal frequency and accuracy of data collected by satellites improves, so too does our ability to monitor floating macroplastics from low-earth orbit. Sentinel-2A & B are optical earth observation satellites launched in 2015 and 2017, respectively. Although the onboard multi-spectral instrument (MSI) sensors were ostensibly developed for terrestrial services, the high resolution (10m, 20m and 60m bands) output also allows for detection of objects in the marine environment, including boats, wind turbines, oil platforms, aquaculture cages, and even rafts of Sargassum seaweed.

At 10m, the highest resolution of Sentinel-2, it is unlikely that individual pieces of floating debris could be detected with any certainty by satellite. However, fronts, eddies and other submesoscale features are known to aggregate floating materials into patches (D'Asaro et al., 2018). We propose that the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 is sufficient to detect aggregated floating objects, likely a mix of materials including macroalgae and other natural sources of debris, as well as anthropogenic sources - increasingly plastic and polystyrene. Being able to detect aggregations of floating debris by satellite may help us to tackle some open questions about sources of macroplastics, as well as pathways, fates, and trends.

5.3.1 Methods

For Sentinel-2 detection of floating debris likely to include macroplastics (mixed debris), we followed several steps and guidelines: First, selection of an area known or likely to have high concentrations of floating macroplastic debris that have recently entered the water. Fast-growing organisms such as algae, barnacles or seaweed adhering to macroplastic can sink objects below the water surface, making detection from satellite impossible. We thus prioritised coastal waters, where macroplastics are likely to have recently entered the ocean from sources such as beaches, rivers, marinas, etc.

Second, used existing datasets. The AWI (Alfred Wegner Institute) LITTERBASE portal collates scientific studies that include or are focused on marine plastics, and summarises results in a mapped global format. We searched for studies that published data on floating macroplastics published after 2010. Twitter was also monitored for tweets containing a range of hashtags pertaining to plastic pollution in marine environments.

Third, focused on coastal waters characterised by strong fronts or eddies, with nearby rivers or ports: sources of floating macroplastics and other debris can originate from land-based sources including rivers, intertidal zones, and ports/ marinas. Fronts, eddies and other submesoscale processes are known to aggregate floating debris into ‘patches’, making detection more likely (D’Asaro et al., 2018)(Möhlenkamp et al., 2018).

Sentinel-2 data were available at no charge, and were downloaded via the European Space Agency (ESA) Copernicus Open Access Hub (<https://schihub.copernicus.eu/>) as Level 1C products. To access these data, a simple registration process was required to generate user login credentials. Once downloaded, the data and imagery were explored and processed in SNAP using the Sentinel toolboxes. SNAP and the associated toolboxes also free to download (step.esa.int/main/download/).

Without going into much detail (See D4-D5), we applied terrestrial atmospheric correction Sen2Cor, which is built into the SNAP toolbox, automatically conserves signals in the NIR and SWIR, making it an appropriate first test for this study. After applying Sen2Cor to retrieve ‘bottom of atmosphere’ values, data were geometrically reprocessed in SNAP (bands resampled to 10m) to ensure rasters were the same size. Then we applied different indices, including the Floating Algae Index (FAI). The FAI algorithm was designed for detecting aquatic vegetation (Hu, 2009). Because it centres around the reflectance peak in the NIR it is, however, suitable for approximating other floating objects too. Further, FAI has advantages over NDVI in that it is less sensitive to changes in parameters related to atmosphere and observation (aerosol type and thickness, solar/viewing angle, and glint), and has been shown to detect floating objects through thin cloud or haze (Hu, 2009).

We compare output from the NDVI and FAI analyses with the assumption that any deviations from a covarying relationship would be due to contributions from the atmosphere, or from floating objects that are not plants. We also assume that high NDVI values point to a higher percentage of macroalgae within a given pixel (well aggregated), rather than healthier plants.

5.3.2 Results

Sentinel-2 imagery from three case studies was investigated, including: Washington State Inner Passage, the East coast of Scotland, and targets deployed by Marine Remote Sensing Group at the University of the Aegean. Full details of the results are presented in D4-D5 OPTIMAL reports. As an illustration we describe part of the results obtained for Washington State Inner Passage here.

Davis and Murphy (2015) published results on extensive study of plastics in Washington State waters. Their work was discovered through the AWI LITTERBASE portal. Using manta trawls, plastic was found in all areas of the Inside Passage, but it was consistently most concentrated in surface waters near harbours and marinas (Davis III and Murphy, 2015). Polystyrene was the dominant source of floating pollution, often in the form of large blocks of expanded foam. Furthermore, in these waters, timber rafting still takes place. Large aggregations of wind and current-driven floating debris tend to be primarily composed of woody material and macroalgae, but increasingly also considerable quantities of foam, plastic bottles and bags, and cans (Davis III and Murphy, 2015). These aggregations are a known hazard to navigation in northern British Columbia and Alaskan waters. This case study focused on the San Juan islands, where highest

concentrations of floating plastics were found. We selected waters off south Gabriola Island as our study site, based on its location near a busy marina and timber rafting area.

Several cloud-free Sentinel-2 images were available from 2017 and 2018, where the waters off south Gabriola did not exhibit high interference from wind-driven white caps. One such image was collected by Sentinel-2B on the 18th of July 2018. As level 1C data, the atmospheric component (scattering and absorption effects) needed to be removed from the reflectance values (surface properties/ characteristics) retrieved by Sentinel-2. We applied Sen2Cor and resampled rasters to 10m for application of the FAI detection algorithm.

Application of the FAI algorithm allowed for detection of floating debris in imagery collected over the San Juan islands. This was especially true for waters off Gabriola Island, where aggregations of floating woody material are often present and shown in Figures 13 , 14 and reffig:macro4; and have been shown to be mixed with macroalgae and macroplastics (Davis III and Murphy, 2015).

Figure 13: Example of a large aggregation of floating debris in waters off south Gabriola Island. This floating patch is likely composed of woody material, macroalgae and plastic, based on previous findings by Davis and Murphy (2015). Not seen is the nearby area where hundreds of logs have been rafted and moored to the shoreline. High resolution imagery provided by Google Earth.

Figure 14: Sentinel-2 MSI true colour image (right), and FAI (left) of our area of interest. Rafted timber, a small boat with wake, and the marina are pointed out. Just off the south Gabriola Island coastline, floating material is evident in the FAI output but not in the true colour image.

Figure 15: Focusing in on the aggregations of mixed floating material off the south Gabriola coastline, a number of bright pixels are evident, and have been pinned accordingly. Spectral shapes here had no peaks in the red edge – Group 1. Pins are coloured in blue, red, orange and green to differentiate between different aggregations or patches of debris (Figure 16). These detections were selected based on similar spectral shapes, though other detections were evident and have been examined separately.

Pixels containing floating matter spectral features were initially separated in two groups (Group 1 and 2). Spectral shapes between Group 1 and Group 2 differ primarily in the red edge bands (705 - 783nm) (Figure 16 and 17 respectively). These 20m resolution bands are normally used for vegetation characterisation, namely: for deriving leaf area index and/or chlorophyll content. As a result, it is possible that Group 2 detections are more indicative of/contain a higher percentage of floating vegetation relative to Group 1. The alternative is that the water contains more chlorophyll. Waters around Gabriola Island and throughout much of the Puget Sound are vulnerable to eutrophication, including large algae blooms, red tides, macro-algae, and jellyfish – especially over the summer months. Our data was collected in July.

Figure 16: Spectral output of floating debris pinned in Figure 15 – Group 1, $n = 27$. Colours are used to separate aggregations detected off south Gabriola Bay. Although reflectance intensities in the visible (490 – 665nm), NIR (842nm) and SWIR (1610nm) do differ between pins within and between aggregations, the spectral shapes from each pixel are relatively consistent. No peaks are evident in the red edge bands (705 – 783nm) (dl = dimensionless measure of intensity – absorption/reflectance).

Figure 17: Aggregations of mixed floating material off the south Gabriola coastline, with a number of bright pixels pinned in different colours to differentiate aggregations or patches. Pixels detected in this group all showed small peaks of reflection in the red edge bands (705 – 783nm) – Group 2.

However, after further investigation, the difference in red edge peaks between Group 1 and Group 2 detections does not appear to play a significant role. For this reason, and because pixels from Group 1 and Group 2 were often directly adjacent, groups were merged (18).

Figure 18: Correlation between FAI and NDVI values for all pixels (Group 1 plus Group 2) represent floating objects off south Gabriola bay. The second-degree polynomial trendline is selected to fit the data ($R^2 = 0.82$).

To compare with other features that may reflect in the NIR but are not floating debris, we created a library of spectral signatures that included the water itself, vessels, wakes, and glint. Figures 19, 19, 20, 21 and 22 illustrate the location and characteristic spectra of glint and vessels selected to form part of false positive marine debris spectra.

Figure 19: Pinned pixels from a range of areas around Gabriola Island, including waters within a wind shadow with no glint (pinned in blue) to waters with high reflectivity from glint (red), with a range selected in between (green to orange).

Figure 20: The spectral shape of water appears to be relatively consistent and flat, no matter where in the Puget Sound pixels were selected. Intensity, however, changes depending with the amount of glint. It is also worth noting small peaks in the red edge throughout, which is either a feature of glint, or is suggestive of some contribution of chlorophyll.

Figure 21: Library: spectral view of glint from waters nearby to Gabriola Island, which are less protected from prevailing winds and are thus relatively choppy.

Figure 22: Library: spectral view of floating vessels in and around our area of interest, with red from a small boat, green showing a medium sized vessel, and 3 blue pins from one large vessel.

5.3.3 Conclusions and further work

By detecting mixed floating debris in the coastal zone, we are aiming to highlight the usefulness of satellite remote sensing for detection of macroplastics, and sources of small plastics, in our global oceans.

The majority of plastic objects floating on the surface of the ocean are likely to be smaller than the highest 10m resolution Sentinel-2 can offer. The likelihood of detecting sub-pixel features depends on satellite sensor sensitivity (signal-to-noise ratio), but mostly on the size of the feature in question (the percentage of a 10m x 10m pixel that is filled by the object). By taking advantage of submesoscale features such as fronts and eddies, which are known to aggregate floating materials into patches (D'Asaro et al., 2018), we thus increase the likelihood of detecting macroplastics and other anthropogenic sources of debris.

The approach outlined in this report is a first approximation of what can be done using high resolution satellite remote sensing data. It is evident from this work that Sentinel-2 maximum spatial resolution of 10m is sufficient to detect aggregated floating objects.

Using a generic terrestrial atmospheric correction and simple detection algorithms designed for plants, floating aggregations of material were detected in two regions – the east coast of Scotland and the waters around Gabriola Island in the Puget Sound. No in situ validation data was collected at the same time as satellite overpasses. However, based on news articles and reports, images shared via social media, and scientific literature published on pollution problems in these areas, these patches are highly likely to include macroplastics. Examining spectral shape proved to be a

robust method for confirming that detected objects were not being confused with other features such as foam, glint, boats, or features of the underlying water type. Furthermore, based on examination the plastic targets placed into the Aegean Sea, there is increased certainty that spectral shape of confirmed plastic generally matches spectral shape of aggregations likely to contain plastic.

The application of a bespoke, fine-tuned atmospheric correction algorithm would go some way to remove uncertainties around signals in the NIR and SWIR bands. Thus, the next stage of this work would focus on improving the atmospheric correction as a first step, leveraging POLYMER for enhanced detection. Indeed, observed spectral variability between detections made in the Puget Sound and east coast of Scotland is likely due to contributions from the intervening atmosphere. On the other hand, variations between detections within the same area are possibly due to varying concentrations of debris, the composition of mixed objects, as well as the amount of time detected objects have spent in the water (biofilm). Further down the line, this information may prove key for quantifying the amount of natural to anthropogenic debris present in a given pixel.

One of the main aims of future work is to automate the process of debris detection by leveraging the CALIMNOS processing chain, treating floating objects as an optical ‘type’. Once the process is automated, multiple areas can be investigated across time for patterns regarding sources, pathways, and roles of underlying submesoscale processes in coastal waters.

Information on how submesoscale processes disperse or aggregate macroplastics is invaluable if it can be extrapolated to gyres and other open ocean processes.

6 Conceptual Design

6.1 Revision of the Compliance Matrix

OPTIMAL has addressed Pre-Phase A (NASA)(NASA, 2016) or Phase 0 (ESA) for a satellite mission, collecting requirements and doing preliminary assessment of radiometric and image-radiometric technologies to detect marine plastic debris from space. As a result from the experimental phase (Section 5) the initial Compliance Matrix (Table 2) can be revised in the form of Table 3.

Table 3: Revision of the Compliance Matrix (Table 3) after the experimental phase of OPTIMAL. Questions (Q) refer to the list of questions in Section 4.3.

Marine Process	Question (Q)	Matching mission and sensor	OPTIMAL assesment
River discharge	Q1	Sentinel-2 MSI	-Spatial and temporal requirements not satisfied -Algorithm validation required in relation with coastal/river-sea fronts
Spills	Q1	Sentinel-2 MSI	-Not included in OPTIMAL
Shoreline accumulation	Q1, Q2, Q3	Sentinel-2 MSI	-Spatial and temporal requirements satisfied -Spectral band missing recommended around 1732 nm
Submesoscale convergence filaments	Q2, Q3	Sentinel-3 OLCI	-Target areas with $Chl \sim 0.05 mgm^{-3}$ - Plastics $D \sim 2 \mu m$ found most relevant

In addition to the characteristics in the revised Compliance Matrix (Table 3), some parameters ranges were also obtained from OPTIMAL as a refinement of requirements. These are presented in detail in D9-OPTIMAL but summarised here in Table 4 and 5. Because of the radiometric interference of pure water on the SWIR, performance parameters have been grouped according to wet scenarios (Table 4) and dry scenarios (Table 5).

Table 4: Performance parameter ranges for the Compliance Matrix in Table 3 incorporating the results from OPTIMAL [D4-D5] for wet plastics detection (i.e. from river discharges and on submesoscale convergence filaments). Where no experimental results are available yet, references from the literature have been used (see footnotes to the Table).

Performance parameters	Spectral range	Spectral resolution	SNR	GSD	Revisit	Coverage
Visible (VIS) and Near-Infra Red (NIR)	350 to 850 nm	Better than 10 nm [*]	VIS >500 NIR >600 [†]	Better than 300 m ^{**}	At least 1 per day ^{**}	Global ^{**}
SWIR	centered on 1732 nm [‡]	Better than 40 nm [§]	>100 [¶]	Better than 20 m ^{**}	At least 1 per day ^{**}	Global ^{**}

^{*}To match current Sentinel-3 capabilities, from laboratory experiments [D4-D5].

[†]VIS requirements mostly achieved by current and planned missions (Sentinel-3 OLCI). NIR requirements related to improvement of atmospheric correction (Qi et al., 2017). From laboratory experiments [D4-D5], an increase in accuracy from 50% to 5% uncertainty in the linear scale would allow concentrations 10 to 100 times higher than the current expected.

^{**}From revised user requirements [D1] and Martínez-Vicente et al. (2019).

[‡]From field aircraft data [D4-D5, Fig.30]. The effect of the level of attenuation by water absorption and/or immersion needs to be further investigated.

[§]Width of absorption peak [D4-D5, Fig. 28 & 29]

[¶]From Sentinel-2 at 1613.7 nm for 20 m GSD. Needs further refinement.

Table 5: Performance parameter ranges for the Compliance Matrix in Table 3 incorporating the results from OPTIMAL [D4-D5] for dry plastic debris measurements (i.e. shoreline accumulation). Current specifications for Sentinel-2 in the VIS were sufficient to detect tested targets, with homogeneous cover and size 10 x 10 m [D4-D5, Fig. 21]. Where no experimental results are available yet, references from the literature have been used (see footnotes to the Table).

Performance parameters	Spectral range	Spectral resolution	SNR	GSD	Revisit	Coverage
SWIR	centered on 1732 nm [‡]	Better than 40 nm [§]	>100 [‡]	Better than 20 m ^{**}	At least 1 per month ^{**}	Global ^{**}

[‡]From field aircraft data [D4-D5, Fig. 30]

[§]Width of absorption peak [D4-D5, Fig. 28 & 29]

[‡]From Sentinel-2 at 1613.7 nm for 20 m GSD. Needs further refinement.

^{**}From revised user requirements [D1] and Martínez-Vicente et al. (2019).

6.2 Conceptual Design elements

Scenarios with wet-plastics have been found to have similar requirements in terms of temporal and spatial observation scales. Also, testing is required in areas of potential accumulation where impacts on the marine environment (but also in other societal important areas, such as navigation) could be greater.

Figure 23 summarises the elements, that include an experimental phase, to refine the SNR. This experimental phase includes testing realistic plastic types, as well as measurements during controlled *in situ* deployments and sampling in the natural environment.

In parallel to an experimental approach, maximum use of current EO assets is necessary, to delimit further the spatial and temporal requirements of the mission. In particular, exploitation of the synergy between hyperspectral and Sentinel-2 data (red line) would be encouraged. Validation of the characteristics (extent, duration, location, causes) of fronts that accumulate marine litter is needed. This would help refine the definition of the spatial and temporal observational characteristics required.

Refinement for more realistic conditions of both SNR and temporal and spatial scales of observation, would help assess the potential of candidate approaches (like HAPS or Cubesats) to deliver best fit-for-purpose observations.

Figure 23: Conceptual diagram to progress towards a system to detect marine plastic litter floating and in the ocean, including the elements and their relationships. A similar approach could be used (removing the fronts element) for marine debris on the shoreline.

A similar conceptual diagram to that in Figure 23 could be applied to the marine plastics on the shore, by removing the box for fronts. In this case, a stronger component of *in situ* could be delivered by drones equipped with short wave near infrared sensors.

A top level conceptual diagram with different elements and their relationships has been presented. A development plan to deliver this will be presented in the next section (and detailed in D9-OPTIMAL).

7 Development plan

The technology for radiometric detection of marine plastic debris is currently at Basic Technology Research level (Technology Readiness Level, TRL, 1-2). OPTIMAL results have demonstrated that in some Scenarios (detection of dry macroplastics), there is potential for detection in idealised conditions (TRL 3), so that further scientific research is needed to test under realistic conditions in the laboratory and in the field (TRL 4 and 5). Therefore the roadmap presented is for **research**

activities in the short and medium term.

7.1 Scientific roadmap elements and processes

The conceptual design proposed includes the following elements (Figure 23):

- **Experimental:** Including laboratory experiments with an increased variety of particle compositions and sizes to create a library of plastic particles comparable with other optically active substances in the ocean. Also target deployment should be included in this experimental phase, including the relevant wavelengths using drone platforms in addition to current satellites (e.g. (Topouzelis et al., 2019)). Finally, a component of *in situ* observations of the relevant plastics (e.g. % coverages or plastic particles of diameter less than $50\mu\text{m}$) would allow for validation of the ranges observable. The *Experimental* results allow modelling of the required SNR, in realistic accumulation conditions (e.g. near the surface) and validation of *Satellite assets*.
- **Satellite assets:** Using existing satellite information, from different sources will allow for refinement and verification of the most relevant temporal and spatial scales of observation for marine litter. In practice, for wet plastics scenarios (i.e. Table 4), the working hypothesis is that some types of fronts in the ocean accumulate marine debris (plastics and no-plastics). Therefore satellite methods for direct detection of oceanographic discontinuities (e.g. fronts (Miller, 2009; Miller and Christodoulou, 2014)) or machine learning techniques should be validated, for instance with very-high resolution imagery (VHRES) and cross-compared with existing satellites (like Sentinel-2). Data from existing satellites (Sentinel-2) should be refined with improved atmospheric correction algorithms and extended to global processing to increase the potential for exploitation and validation. Synergy of hyperspectral sensors (HYPERS) with finer spatial resolution sensors should also be investigated.

In terms of the *Experimental* (E) elements the following activities should be carried out for testing the scenarios considered:

- E.1 Simulation of the effects of vertical structure of microplastic on the radiative transfer of light through the water column and its impact on the SNR at satellite height.
- E.2 Spectral characterisation of a wide range of sizes and compositions of marine plastics, including bio-fouled and weathered plastics, as well as standard reference plastics.
- E.3 Laboratory experiments of the effects of immersion and level of wetness on the signal retrieved in the SWIR range.
- E.4 *In situ* controlled deployment of plastics in concurrence with hyperspectral measurements.
- E.5 To collect relevant *in situ* observations and to compile a dataset that allows direct comparisons with marine plastic debris estimates as well as to evaluate the existing amounts of marine plastic debris, if possible in areas of accumulation (e.g. very polluted shores and/or oceanic discontinuities).

The outcomes of the *Experimental* phase should be fed into the refinement of the SNR computations (e.g. following (Qi et al., 2017)) both for the VIS and SWIR ranges.

Concerning the *Satellite Assets* (SA), the following activities are recommended:

- SA.1 Development/testing of improved atmospheric correction algorithms for Sentinel-2 to evaluate current capabilities.
- SA.2 To produce an operational processing of Sentinel-2 to maximise the possibilities of validation of marine debris accumulation.
- SA.3 To investigate and validate methods for oceanographic discontinuities (such as fronts or windrows) where there is potential for marine plastic debris accumulation, using solely Remote sensing assets. Methods such as front detection using sea surface temperature or ocean colour or machine learning methods should be investigated.
- SA.4 To use very high resolution imagery for validation or in synergy with other satellite assets such as hyperspectral and multispectral imagers (Sentinel-2 MSI).

In addition to the strictly scientific activities, some higher level linkages need to be established:

- **Linkages with other space agencies.** NASA is currently developing relevant missions at different stages of development. PACE is at an advanced development stage, and initial requirements review is occurring for the Surface Biology and Geology mission (SBG). Interaction with NASA and other space agencies (e.g. JAXA) should be achieved.
- **International community development.** The on-going SCOR WG153 Flotsam (Floating Litter and its Oceanic Transport Analysis and Modelling) is serving as an initial platform for creating a community of scientists and users for marine plastic debris products from space. This type of international coordinating and network activity should be supported in the future.

These higher level science-policy activities could be lead under the auspices of the International Ocean Color Coordinating Group (IOCCG, <https://ioccg.org/>), by submitting a proposal for a new working group that could coordinate internationally all these activities.

8 Scientific impact and assessment

The scientific impact of the project can be assessed using a set of metrics:

- **The OPTIMAL ESA reports:** The scientific rationale, progress, results and products are described in a series of reports

D1-D2 Application Analysis and Marine Litter mission requirements (initial)

D3 Techniques and technologies assessment

D4-D5 Methods and experimental results

D6 Conceptual Design Specifications

D9 Scientific Development plan

- **Scientific Publications published, submitted and in preparation:**

- Martínez-Vicente, V., Clark, J. R., Corradi, P., Aliani, S., Arias, M., Bochow, M., Bonnery, G., Cole, M., Cózar, A., Donnelly, R., and et al. (2019). Measuring marine plastic debris from space: Initial assessment of observation requirements. *Remote Sensing*, 11(20):2443.

- Maximenko, N., Corradi, P., Law, K. L., Van Sebille, E., Garaba, S. P., Lampitt, R. S., Galgani, F., Martinez-Vicente, V., Goddijn-Murphy, L., Veiga, J. M., and et al. (2019). Toward the integrated marine debris observing system. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6.
- Sebille, E. v., Aliani, S., Law, K. L., Maximenko, N., Alsina, J., Bagaev, A., Bergmann, M., Chapron, B., Chubarenko, I., Cózar, A., and et al. (2020). The physical oceanography of the transport of floating marine debris. *Environmental Research Letters*.
- Biermann et al. *accepted Feb-2020*. Finding Plastic Patches in Coastal Waters using Optical Satellite Data
- Martinez-Vicente et al. *in preparation*. Ocean colour anomaly caused by oceanic small plastic particles.
- Mata et al. *in preparation*. Optical Remote Sensing Detection Of Plastic Targets On The Shore: Field Campaign And Modelling Results.

- **International Conferences and Workshops**

- Martinez-Vicente et al. Optical Methods for Marine Litter Detection (OPTIMAL): From User Requirements To Recommendations For A Mission Roadmap. Oral. ESA Atlantic from Space workshop. Southampton , February 2019.
- Lauren Biermann, Victor Martinez Vicente, Sevrine Sailley, Aser Mata, and Christopher Steele, Towards a method for detecting macroplastics by satellite: examining Sentinel-2 earth observation data for floating debris in the coastal zone. Oral. EGU General Assembly, Viena, April 2019.
- Martinez-Vicente et al. Optical Methods for Marine Litter Detection (OPTIMAL): From User Requirements To Recommendations For A Mission Roadmap. Oral. ESA Living Planet Symposium. Milan , May 2019.
- Mata et al. Optical Remote Sensing Detection Of Plastic Targets On The Shore: Field Campaign And Modelling Results. Poster. ESA Living Planet Symposium. Milan , May 2019.

- **News:**

- BBC interview to L. Biermann: Can you spot ocean plastic from space? <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/science-environment-47910600>

9 Forward look

The main points of the forward look are summarised in the D9 - Development plan. These focus on the main scenarios addressed by OPTIMAL, which have been : the open ocean accumulation areas , like the fronts; and the shoreline accumulation. Some additional points are made here. From Table 3, another important Scenario are rivers as pathways of marine plastics to the ocean.

Increased spatial and temporal monitoring of plastic litter input from rivers, especially in Asia, are a benchmark against which to judge the effectiveness of future management scenarios, therefore supporting national governments in the area to achieve targets within the wider remit of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). In particular, it has been recently proposed that Space Agencies should take the lead on developing global indicators for supporting monitoring of marine

plastic litter under SDG14 [Expert workshop in Paris UN, September 2018 and GESMAP,2019]. However, maturity of the relevant indicator (i.e. sub indicator for Marine Litter under Indicator 14.1.1) is very low, meaning that no international standards are available or have been yet agreed. Work towards the development and validation, in realistic conditions, of a marine plastic litter indicator from Earth Observation would support wider acceptance by the UN.

Because of the importance of Asian rivers as pathways of marine litter into the ocean (Lebreton et al., 2017), a method developed to remotely estimate marine plastic litter from rivers in the South East Asiatic region would have a significant impact both in refining global budgets and providing tools for environmental monitoring to guide mitigation strategies.

10 Conclusions

OPTIMAL was a science-driven project that relied on multiple user consultation activities to ensure that the activities and the outcomes were tailor made to meet the requirements of the user community. It has achieved its main objectives and delivered valuable scientific outputs, serving as a basis to the Remote sensing component for a future marine debris observing system (Maximenko et al. (2019)Martínez-Vicente et al. (2019)). The main conclusions of OPTIMAL can be summarised as follows:

- The user requirements have been refined through experiments in the laboratory, a field campaign and a satellite based study. Table 3 summarises the revised compliance matrix, incorporating implications for requirements derived from the experimental study, alongside boundaries for performance parameters ranges (Tables 4 and Table 5).
- Nanoplastics could be potentially detectable at extremely high concentrations in areas of the ocean with very low chlorophyll concentrations using radiometry in the visible part of the spectrum.
- Aircraft mounted hyperspectral radiometers have confirmed spectral features of plastics in the shortwave infrared for dry plastic targets (on the shoreline).
- Sentinel-2 images have provided preliminary evidence of large aggregations of debris material, including plastics, over fronts.
- Taking advantage of the experimental, modelling and Earth Observation study, a Conceptual Design and a Development plan have been produced. Given the initial level of development of the radiometric approach for the specific application of marine plastic debris detection, the Conceptual plan is mostly proposed in terms of a **Scientific Roadmap**, to progress from fundamental science to more realistic situations. In parallel to producing specifications for a marine plastics debris sensor, current Earth Observation assets should be used to develop "indirect indices". For instance, to create "risk maps" from oceanographic discontinuities that are likely to accumulate marine debris, like fronts or windrows. A greater coordination at the international level of the scientific community at the boundary between earth observation and marine plastic debris scientists should be encouraged to address the problem of plastics debris remote sensing detection in the marine environment at the global scale.

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